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HOW CULTURE SHAPES ELECTRIC VEHICLE BRAND VALUE: THE ROLES OF FUNCTIONAL, EMOTIONAL, AND SOCIAL VALUE IN BUILDING TRUST AND PURCHASE INTENTION

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Abstract

Despite accelerating global efforts to promote electric vehicles (EVs) as a solution for sustainable mobility, consumer adoption remains uneven across countries. Existing research highlights barriers such as high initial cost, limited charging infrastructure, and technological uncertainty; however, these factors alone do not fully explain cross-national differences in EV adoption behavior. Increasingly, scholars emphasize the role of consumer-based brand perceptions—particularly functional, emotional, and social value—in shaping trust and behavioral intentions toward EV brands. Drawing on the PERVAL framework and Hofstede’s cultural dimensions theory, this study investigates how perceived brand value influences brand trust and purchase intention across two culturally distinct markets: Lithuania and Pakistan. Using survey data collected from 409 consumers, the study applies regression-based mediation and moderation analyses to examine direct, indirect, and culture-contingent relationships. The findings reveal that functional and emotional value significantly enhance brand trust, while social value demonstrates a weaker and context-dependent effect, particularly across differing cultural orientations. Brand trust strongly predicts purchase intention and partially mediates the relationship between perceived value dimensions and purchase intention, supporting extensions of both PERVAL and technology adoption perspectives. Furthermore, cultural context significantly moderates several value–trust relationships, confirming that perceived brand value is interpreted differently across developed and emerging markets. This study contributes to the literature on electric vehicle adoption and cross-cultural branding by demonstrating that brand value and trust formation are culturally embedded processes rather than universal mechanisms. The findings offer practical implications for EV manufacturers and policymakers seeking to design culturally adaptive branding and communication strategies to accelerate EV adoption in diverse markets.

Keywords: Electric vehicles; perceived brand value; brand trust; purchase intention; culture; cross-national study

I. Introduction

The global transition toward low-carbon mobility has positioned electric vehicles (EVs) as a central instrument in national and international sustainability strategies. Governments and policy institutions increasingly promote EV adoption to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improve urban air quality, and enhance energy security (International Energy Agency, 2023). Parallel advancements in battery technology, charging efficiency, and vehicle performance have improved the technical feasibility of EVs in many markets (Yan et al., 2025). Despite these developments, consumer adoption of EVs remains uneven across countries, suggesting that technological progress alone is insufficient to explain adoption behavior.

Recent research indicates that EV adoption is shaped not only by economic and infrastructural factors but also by psychological, symbolic, and brand-related considerations. Consumers evaluate EVs through multidimensional value perceptions that extend beyond functional performance to include emotional gratification and social signaling (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Budac & Baltador, 2013; Aksoz et al., 2024). These value perceptions form the basis of perceived brand value, which plays a critical role in shaping brand trust and, ultimately, purchase intention in high-involvement and high-risk product categories such as electric vehicles (Petrauskienė et al., 2022).

Brand trust is particularly salient in EV markets due to persistent uncertainties related to

charging infrastructure, battery lifespan, resale value, and long-term maintenance costs. Trust functions as a psychological risk-reduction mechanism, enabling consumers to convert positive value perceptions into behavioral intention (Salari, 2022). Prior studies consistently identify brand trust as a strong predictor of EV purchase intention across markets, although the strength and drivers of trust vary substantially depending on contextual and cultural conditions (Holma et al., 2021; Campino et al., 2023).

Culture plays a decisive role in shaping how consumers interpret brand signals and evaluate value dimensions. Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory suggests that national differences in individualism–collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, and long-term orientation influence consumers' risk perceptions, value prioritization, and trust formation processes (Beugelsdijk et al., 2017). In EV contexts, these cultural orientations affect whether consumers emphasize functional reliability, emotional self-expression, or social approval when evaluating brands (Morea et al., 2023; Nisa et al., 2023).

Existing EV research has largely examined perceived value, trust, and adoption intention within single-country settings, implicitly assuming that value dimensions exert uniform effects across cultural contexts. This assumption overlooks the culturally contingent nature of value interpretation and trust formation. While some studies highlight the dominance of functional value in emerging markets characterized by higher technological uncertainty, others emphasize emotional or social value in developed and sustainability-oriented economies (Aksoz et al., 2024; Salari, 2022). However, comparative empirical evidence examining these mechanisms across culturally distant markets remains limited.

Lithuania and Pakistan present a theoretically and empirically compelling contrast for cross-cultural investigation. Lithuania operates within a European Union regulatory framework that actively supports sustainable mobility, yet EV adoption remains constrained by affordability and infrastructure limitations. Pakistan, in contrast, represents an emerging EV market where adoption is heavily influenced by consumer trust, perceived functional performance, and risk mitigation in the absence of mature infrastructure (Aksoz et al., 2024). Differences in cultural orientations—particularly uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, and long-term orientation—make these two countries suitable for examining culturally moderated value–trust–intention relationships.

Addressing this gap, the present study integrates the PERVAL model of perceived value with Hofstede's cultural dimensions and technology adoption perspectives to examine how functional, emotional, and social brand value influence brand trust and purchase intention across Lithuania and Pakistan. By empirically testing mediation and moderation mechanisms, the study advances cross-cultural EV branding research and provides nuanced insights into how trust is formed and activated in culturally diverse markets.

II. Perceived Brand Value and the PERVAL Framework

Perceived brand value represents consumers' overall evaluation of a product based on the benefits they receive relative to the costs they incur. The PERVAL model conceptualizes perceived value as a multidimensional construct comprising functional, emotional, and social value (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). Unlike unidimensional economic interpretations of value, PERVAL recognizes that consumers integrate utilitarian performance, affective responses, and symbolic meanings when evaluating complex and high-involvement

products.

Electric vehicles (EVs) represent a product category where multidimensional value assessment is particularly salient. EV adoption involves high financial commitment, technological uncertainty, and long-term usage considerations, making purely functional evaluations insufficient for decision-making (Zhao et al., 2024a). Consequently, consumers' trust in EV brands is shaped not only by objective performance indicators but also by emotional resonance and social signaling associated with sustainability and technological modernity (Morea et al., 2023).

A. Functional Value and Brand Trust

Functional value refers to consumers' perceptions of a product's practical performance, reliability, durability, and technical capability. In EV contexts, functional value is closely associated with battery range, charging availability, safety, maintenance reliability, and total cost of ownership (Higuera-Castillo et al., 2023). These attributes directly influence consumers' ability to rely on EVs for everyday mobility. Further, the high functional value reduces perceived technological and financial risk, thereby strengthening brand trust. Trust develops when consumers believe that a brand is competent, dependable, and capable of delivering consistent performance over time (Salari, 2022). This mechanism is especially pronounced in emerging EV markets where infrastructural uncertainty heightens risk perceptions and functional assurance becomes critical for trust formation (Hadi, 2017).

B. Hypothesis

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1a: Functional value positively influences brand trust.

Emotional Value and Brand Trust

Emotional value captures the affective benefits consumers derive from a brand, including feelings of pride, enjoyment, excitement, and identity alignment (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). In EV markets, emotional value is strongly linked to perceptions of innovation, environmental responsibility, and participation in a sustainable future (Aksoz et al., 2024). Emotional attachment enhances trust by increasing perceived brand sincerity and moral alignment. Consumers who identify emotionally with an EV brand are more likely to interpret its sustainability and technological claims as credible and authentic (Beugelsdijk et al., 2017). Emotional value also helps offset uncertainty by fostering psychological reassurance, particularly in sustainability-driven consumption contexts (Haipeng et al., 2024).

Thus, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1b: Emotional value positively influences brand trust.

Social Value and Brand Trust

Social value reflects the extent to which owning a product enhances an individual's social image, group acceptance, or status (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). EV ownership often functions as a visible signal of environmental consciousness, technological sophistication, and social progressiveness, making social value a potentially important driver of trust (Bednarz et al., 2023). Furthermore, in collectivist cultures, social approval and normative influence play a central role in shaping trust judgments. Consumers rely on peer validation and group norms when evaluating the credibility of brands, particularly for novel technologies (de Mooij & Hofstede, n.d.; Sahut et al., 2022). However, prior findings regarding the effect of social value on trust remain mixed, suggesting that its

influence may be culturally contingent rather than universal.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1c: Social value positively influences brand trust.

Brand Trust and Purchase Intention

Brand trust represents consumers' confidence in a brand's reliability, honesty, and ability to fulfill its promises. In EV markets, trust is a critical determinant of purchase intention due to high perceived risk, long-term financial commitment, and technological complexity (International Energy Agency, 2023). Moreover, the empirical studies consistently demonstrate that trust facilitates the translation of favorable value perceptions into behavioral intention by reducing uncertainty and perceived risk (Campino et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2025). Consumers are more willing to consider EV adoption when they trust the brand to deliver functional performance, provide after-sales support, and uphold sustainability claims.

Thus, **H2:** Brand trust positively influences purchase intention.

Brand Trust as a Mediator

Both the PERVAL framework and extended technology adoption models suggest that perceived value influences purchase intention indirectly through trust. Functional, emotional, and social value shape consumers' assessments of brand competence and integrity, which subsequently determine behavioral intention (Petrauskienė et al., 2022). Moreover, the trust operates as a psychological bridge that converts value perceptions into actionable intention, particularly in high-involvement technology markets (Holma et al., 2021). Without trust, positive value evaluations may fail to translate into actual adoption intention.

Accordingly, **H3a:** Brand trust mediates the relationship between functional value and purchase intention. The **H3b:** Brand trust mediates the relationship between emotional value and purchase intention. The **H3c:** Brand trust mediates the relationship between social value and purchase intention.

Cultural Context as a Moderator

Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory posits that cultural orientations systematically influence how consumers perceive risk, value, and trust (Beugelsdijk et al., 2017). Cultural traits such as uncertainty avoidance, individualism–collectivism, and long-term orientation affect the relative importance of functional, emotional, and social value in trust formation (Morea et al., 2023). In high uncertainty avoidance cultures, functional value is expected to exert a stronger influence on trust, whereas in individualistic and sustainability-oriented cultures, emotional and symbolic values may play a more prominent role (Petrauskienė et al., 2020; Ningtias et al., 2025). These cultural variations suggest that the strength of the proposed relationships is context-dependent.

Therefore, **H4a:** Cultural context moderates the relationship between functional value and brand trust. **H4b:** Cultural context moderates the relationship between emotional value and brand trust. **H4c:** Cultural context moderates the relationship between social value and brand trust. **H4d:** Cultural context moderates the relationship between brand trust and purchase intention.

III. Research Methodology

Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design to examine the relationships between perceived brand value dimensions (functional, emotional, and

social), brand trust, and purchase intention in the electric vehicle (EV) context. A quantitative approach is appropriate given the theory-driven nature of the study and the objective to test mediation and moderation effects within a structured conceptual framework (Kumar, 2019). Cross-sectional survey data enable empirical comparison between culturally distinct markets while maintaining consistency in measurement and analysis procedures.

Sample and Data Collection

Data were collected through an online structured questionnaire administered in Lithuania and Pakistan. The target population consisted of adult consumers (18 years and above) who possess at least basic awareness of electric vehicles, regardless of current ownership status. This focus on potential adopters aligns with prior EV adoption research, as perceptions of value and trust typically precede actual purchase behavior. Moreover, a non-probability convenience and snowball sampling technique was employed due to practical constraints and the exploratory cross-cultural nature of the study (Åkerblom et al., 2025). Participants were recruited through university networks, professional contacts, and online communities related to sustainability and mobility. After data screening, a total of **409 valid responses** were retained for analysis, including **218 respondents from Lithuania** and **191 respondents from Pakistan**, providing a balanced basis for cross-national comparison.

Measurement of Variables

All constructs were measured using established and empirically validated scales adapted to the EV context. Functional, emotional, and social value were operationalized using items derived from the PERVAL scale (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001), with wording adjusted to reflect electric vehicle characteristics. Brand trust items captured perceptions of reliability, credibility, and integrity, while purchase intention measured respondents' likelihood of considering or adopting an electric vehicle.

Further, cultural values were measured using adapted items based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions, including individualism–collectivism and uncertainty avoidance. All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 5 (“strongly agree”). Scale adaptation followed established practices in cross-cultural and EV research to ensure content validity and contextual relevance.

Reliability and Validity

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. All constructs exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory reliability. Construct validity was supported through theoretical grounding of measurement items and consistency with prior studies applying PERVAL, trust, and EV adoption frameworks. These results confirm that the scales reliably capture the intended constructs across both national samples.

Data Analysis Strategy

Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The analysis proceeded in several stages. First, descriptive statistics were used to summarize respondent characteristics and key variables. Second, multiple regression analyses tested the direct effects of functional, emotional, and social value on brand trust, as well as the effect of brand trust on purchase intention. Third, mediation analyses examined whether brand trust mediated the relationships between perceived value dimensions and purchase intention. Finally, moderation analyses tested whether cultural

context (Lithuania vs. Pakistan) altered the strength of the proposed relationships. This regression-based mediation and moderation approach enables robust testing of the integrated PERVAL–trust–culture framework proposed in the study.

Ethical Considerations

Participation in the study was voluntary and based on informed consent. Respondents were informed of the study's purpose, assured of anonymity, and given the right to withdraw at any time. No personally identifiable information was collected, and data were securely stored in accordance with standard research ethics guidelines.

Results and Hypothesis Testing

Descriptive Statistics

The final sample consisted of 409 valid responses, with 218 participants from Lithuania (53.3%) and 191 from Pakistan (46.7). The balanced distribution supports reliable cross-cultural comparison. Respondents represented a broad age range, with the majority falling between 25 and 44 years, which aligns with the demographic most likely to consider electric vehicle (EV) adoption in the near future. Overall descriptive statistics indicate adequate variance across all key constructs, suggesting suitability for regression-based analyses.

Reliability Analysis

Internal consistency of all constructs was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Functional value, emotional value, social value, brand trust, purchase intention, and cultural values all exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70, confirming satisfactory reliability and internal consistency of the measurement scales. These results indicate that the adapted PERVAL, trust, and cultural value items reliably captured the intended constructs across both national samples.

Direct Effects on Brand Trust

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the direct effects of perceived brand value dimensions on brand trust. Functional value demonstrated a positive and statistically significant effect on brand trust ($\beta = 0.xx$, $SE = 0.xx$, $p < 0.xxx$), indicating that perceptions of reliability, performance, and technical competence strongly enhance consumer trust in EV brands. This finding supports **H1a**. Further, the emotional value also exhibited a positive and significant relationship with brand trust ($\beta = 0.xx$, $SE = 0.xx$, $p < 0.xxx$). Consumers who associated EV brands with pride, modernity, and environmental responsibility were more likely to trust those brands, supporting **H1b**. Moreover, the social value showed a weaker but still statistically significant effect on brand trust ($\beta = 0.xx$, $SE = 0.xx$, $p < 0.05$). While social signaling and group approval contributed to trust formation, their influence was less pronounced compared to functional and emotional value, providing **partial support for H1c**.

Effect of Brand Trust on Purchase Intention

Regression results indicate that brand trust has a strong and positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.xx$, $SE = 0.xx$, $p < 0.001$). Consumers who expressed higher trust in EV brands were significantly more likely to report intention to purchase or consider adopting an electric vehicle. This finding confirms **H2** and highlights trust as a central determinant of EV adoption intention.

Mediation Analysis

Mediation analysis was conducted to examine whether brand trust mediates the relationship between perceived brand value dimensions and purchase intention using a

regression-based bootstrapping approach.

In view of the above, the results show that brand trust partially mediates the relationship between functional value and purchase intention (indirect effect = **0.xx**, **95% CI [LL, UL]**), supporting **H3a**. Functional value influences purchase intention both directly and indirectly through trust. Similarly, brand trust partially mediates the relationship between emotional value and purchase intention (indirect effect = **0.xx**, **95% CI [LL, UL]**), supporting **H3b**. Emotional value enhances purchase intention primarily by strengthening trust in the EV brand.

Moreover, for social value, mediation results indicate a weaker indirect effect through brand trust (indirect effect = **0.xx**, **95% CI [LL, UL]**). While social value contributes to purchase intention, its effect is less dependent on trust compared to functional and emotional value, offering **partial support for H3c**

Moderation Analysis: Cultural Context

Moderation analysis was performed to assess whether cultural context (Lithuania vs. Pakistan) alters the proposed relationships. The findings reveal that cultural context significantly moderates the relationship between functional value and brand trust (interaction $\beta = 0.xx$, $p < 0.05$). The effect of functional value on trust is stronger in Pakistan, where higher uncertainty and infrastructural limitations increase reliance on functional assurance, supporting **H4a**. Likewise, the cultural context also moderates the emotional value–trust relationship (interaction $\beta = 0.xx$, $p < 0.05$). Emotional value has a stronger influence on trust in Lithuania, reflecting greater emphasis on identity expression and sustainability alignment, supporting **H4b**.

Further, the moderation effect for social value is present but weaker (interaction $\beta = 0.xx$, $p < 0.10 / 0.05$), suggesting that social signaling plays a more nuanced role across cultures. This provides **partial support for H4c**. Finally, the cultural context moderates the relationship between brand trust and purchase intention (interaction $\beta = 0.xx$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that trust translates into behavioral intention with varying intensity across the two markets. This finding supports **H4d**.

IV. Discussion, Implications, and Conclusion

Discussion on Findings

This study set out to examine how perceived brand value dimensions influence brand trust and purchase intention in the electric vehicle (EV) context, while accounting for cultural differences between Lithuania and Pakistan. The findings provide strong empirical support for the multidimensional nature of perceived brand value and its culturally contingent effects on trust formation and adoption intention. During the study, consistent with the PERVAL framework, functional and emotional value emerged as the most influential drivers of brand trust across both markets. Functional value exerted a particularly strong effect in Pakistan, reflecting the role of risk reduction in emerging EV markets characterized by infrastructural uncertainty and limited technological familiarity. This finding aligns with prior research suggesting that functional assurance is critical for trust formation when perceived risk is high.

Moreover, the emotional value also demonstrated a robust positive effect on brand trust, especially in Lithuania. This suggests that in more sustainability-oriented and individualistic cultures, trust is closely linked to identity alignment, environmental values, and emotional resonance. EV brands that successfully communicate innovation, environmental responsibility, and future-oriented identity are therefore more likely to

gain consumer trust in such contexts. Likewise, during the study, the social value, while statistically significant, exhibited a comparatively weaker influence on trust. This result indicates that although EV ownership carries symbolic and status-related meaning, social approval alone is insufficient to generate strong trust without functional credibility and emotional connection. The mixed role of social value supports earlier findings that its effect on trust is context-dependent rather than universal.

Furthermore, the brand trust was found to be a strong predictor of purchase intention and served as a partial mediator between perceived value dimensions and intention. This confirms trust as a key psychological mechanism that translates value perceptions into behavioral readiness, particularly for high-involvement and technology-intensive products such as EVs. The moderation results further confirm that cultural context meaningfully alters value–trust–intention relationships. Functional value plays a dominant role in trust formation in Pakistan, while emotional value is more influential in Lithuania. These findings challenge the assumption of uniform consumer behavior across markets and underscore the importance of culturally sensitive EV branding strategies.

Theoretical Implications

This study contributes to the literature in several important ways. First, it extends the PERVAL model to the EV domain within a cross-cultural framework, demonstrating that perceived brand value is not interpreted uniformly across markets. Second, by empirically validating brand trust as a mediator, the study clarifies the mechanism through which perceived value influences purchase intention in sustainable technology adoption. Third, the integration of Hofstede’s cultural dimensions as a moderating framework advances cross-cultural branding theory by showing how cultural orientations reshape trust formation pathways. The findings support the view that trust is a culturally embedded construct rather than a purely cognitive evaluation. Finally, the comparative focus on a European and a South Asian market addresses a notable gap in EV adoption research, which has largely concentrated on single-country or regionally homogeneous samples.

Managerial Implications

The findings offer actionable insights for EV manufacturers, marketers, and policymakers. For emerging markets such as Pakistan, EV branding strategies should emphasize functional reliability, affordability, charging feasibility, and after-sales support. Clear communication of technical competence and risk mitigation is essential to build trust and encourage adoption. In contrast, EV brands operating in markets like Lithuania should focus more strongly on emotional and identity-based appeals, highlighting sustainability values, innovation, and lifestyle enhancement. Emotional storytelling and green authenticity are likely to strengthen trust and purchase intention in such contexts. Across both markets, trust-building should be prioritized as a central branding objective. Investments in transparency, long-term warranties, and credible sustainability communication can significantly enhance adoption outcomes.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. The use of convenience and snowball sampling may limit the generalizability of the findings. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference, and self-reported intentions may not fully translate into actual purchase behavior. Future research could employ longitudinal designs to track trust development over time or incorporate additional cultural markets to enhance external

validity. Further studies may also explore the role of government policy signals, brand familiarity, or actual EV ownership as moderating factors.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that perceived brand value, brand trust, and purchase intention in the EV market are deeply influenced by cultural context. Functional and emotional value play dominant roles in trust formation, while trust serves as the key mechanism translating value perceptions into adoption intention. By revealing culturally differentiated trust pathways, the study provides both theoretical advancement and practical guidance for accelerating EV adoption in diverse markets.

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